

THE SOCIAL-PHILOSOPHICAL NEED OF DEVELOPING THE HISTORICAL-ANALYTICAL THINKING OF YOUTH

Abdurakhmanov Aliyorjon Abdukhakhorovich

Teacher of the Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences of the
External Department of Fergana State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074110>

Abstract: In this article, the socio-philosophical necessity of developing the historical-analytical thinking of young people and the foundations of forming the ability of analytical analysis of historical data in the information society of young people are researched.

Key words: historical-analytical thinking, information society, historical consciousness and memory, culture of information consumption, historical thinking.

Today, the development of the information society, the expansion of the information field, the decrease in the ability to control and synthesize information, the ability to separate fiction from the truth, express an adequate opinion on reality, and have an objective attitude are decreasing. This brings out the need to combine historical memory and analytical thinking in people.

At the current stage of social development, the aspirations of the citizens of our country, especially the youth, to improve historical knowledge are highly commendable. Today's youth have the right to be proud of their history, the material and spiritual wealth created by their ancestors. After all, "history endures everything. But he cannot bear to fake himself»[1]. Therefore, the study of history sharpens our thinking, allows us to be proud of the history of the past, and to be free from the mistakes made in the future. "The study of history - says the great German enlightener of the 18th century, Friedrich Schiller, - illuminates our mind, ignites our heart with noble devotion. It keeps our soul from approaching moral issues with humility and pettiness»[2]. That is why studying history based on an analytical approach, developing analytical historical thinking is very important for the social activity of today's youth.

This paragraph analyzes the social necessity of developing historical-analytical thinking among young people, the possibilities of eliminating the existing shortcomings in the development of historical thinking, and ways of solving them.

Learning to develop analytical thinking in collaboration with philosophy, psychology, and pedagogic sciences ensures the effectiveness of this process. In this regard, the issue of organizing the mental activity of young people is of great importance. For this reason, we studied thinking, analytical thinking, its essence, peculiarities of formation and possibilities from available literature.

First of all, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the concept of "thinking". In "Philosophy: an encyclopedic dictionary" the concept of "thinking" is defined as follows: "Thinking (Arab. - thinking, intellectual knowledge) is a rational stage of knowledge that determines the common, important characteristics of objects and events, reflects internal, necessary connections, and legal connections between them. "[3].

According to the doctor of psychology, professor E. Goziev, "thinking is the highest form of human mental activity, intellectual intelligence, conscious movement. Thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social environment and reality, as well as the main condition for rational implementation of a wide range of human activities»[4].

According to the psychologist scientist E.Z.Usmonova, thinking is a process that is formed in the conditions of social life, and it first manifests itself in the form of wide subject (practical) activity, and then it becomes a form that takes the character of "mental" behavior [5].

Another scientist Q. Shonazarov proposed the following set of definitions of the concept of "thinking": thinking means the conscious reflection of reality with its objective features, connections, and relationships that cannot be directly perceived by a person; thinking begins when a problem arises for which there is no ready solution. A person begins to think when the need to know something arises; thinking is the activity of the mind aimed at clearly, deeply, completely and directly summarizing and directly reflecting (knowing) reality; thinking is the process of summarizing and reflecting objects and events with their legal connections and relationships in the human brain; thinking is a process of direct and generalized reflection of reality in the process of analysis, synthesis, socially related to the search and discovery of new things; thinking is a cognitive process aimed at indirectly and generalized reflection of the individual; thinking is an active perception of objective reality; It is the formation, movement and development of knowledge in the form of concepts, considerations, thoughts, conclusions, theories and theories [6].

According to another definition, thinking is the highest form of human mental activity; the process of reflection of objective reality in the mind. Thought is considered a tool for knowing the environment, social phenomena, reality, as well as the main condition for human activity. It is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and clearly than intuition, perception, and imagination. In the process of thinking, thoughts, opinions, ideas, hypotheses, etc. are formed in a person's mind, and they are expressed in the form of concepts, judgments, conclusions. Through human thinking, it summarizes reality and indirectly (indirectly), realizes the most important connections, relationships, and characteristics between things and events. Therefore, a person has the ability to foresee the emergence, development and consequences of social events and events based on certain laws, regulations and rules.

Fiqr means thinking, idea, mind, thinking, reflection in Arabic.

1. A thought, imagination about something, event or someone.
2. Judgment, conclusion expressing the attitude towards something, its assessment.

Comparative study of things and events, result of reasoning, stop, decision [7].

According to another definition, thinking is an active perception of objective reality, the formation, movement and development of knowledge in the form of concepts, reasoning, thoughts, conclusions, theories. Continuous learning and especially problem-based learning, its inherent dialogic nature, the speed of forms and methods, help to develop thinking.

In the process of thinking, thoughts arise, these thoughts take the form of important concepts in the mind of a person. Thought is closely connected with speech - language. Because man has thought and speech, he is different from animals, and therefore he is a conscious being. A person consciously perceives objects and events in the world around him, consciously remembers and remembers, and acts consciously.

Thinking in relation to sensations and perceptions, memory and imagination is of particular importance in people's cognitive and practical activities. In the process of thinking, a person determines the correctness, accuracy and authenticity of his perception, imagination and thoughts, whether they are in accordance with reality or not.

Reality is reflected deeper and more fully in thought than in perception and imagination. A person learns things or events that cannot be known by means of intuition, perception and imagination, the characteristics of these things or events, their connections and relationships by means of thinking. Thinking allows us to anticipate events and events, and this process allows us to set goals and act on them. Thanks to foresight and knowledge of the properties of objects in the world, the current human experience has arisen, which opens up the possibility of engaging in a variety of labor. Therefore, thinking is such a mental activity of a person that allows the most accurate, complete, deep and generalized reflection of reality, and allows a person to engage in more reasonable practical activities.

Thinking is formed directly related to the age characteristics of a person. According to the results of psychological-pedagogical studies, the child has the ability to perceive certain things and forgive certain feelings from the day of his birth. But this child cannot yet think; as the child grows up, as he gains experience, the opportunity to communicate through speech expands, as his activity grows, his thinking also grows in the process of education and upbringing.

A concept is formed from judgments connected to each other about things - their properties, states, connections and relations. Forming an understanding of something means making a number of judgments about it. The judgments that reveal the concept make up the content of this concept. The more we can judge about something, the richer the content of the concept. The more important the signs of things expressed in these judgments, the deeper the content of the concept [8].

A concept is a form of thinking that reflects common important features of things and events. It is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that the concept is fundamentally different from the forms of emotional cognition. A concept is not a concrete image of an object, but an abstract image. As the concept deviates from the non-essential features of the object, it cannot fully reflect it. In this sense, it stands apart from existence in relation to sensory forms of cognition. However, the understanding expresses the existence more deeply and fully compared to the forms of emotional knowledge by perceiving the important signs of the object and reflecting its essence. Unlike emotional forms of cognition, the concept is not directly reflected in the human brain. It is formed using certain logical methods of comparison, analysis, synthesis, abstraction, generalizations. The formation of the concept is inextricably linked with the word. The connection between them is that the connection between thought and language is clearly invisible.

In conclusion, through the development of historical knowledge, a historical-analytical outlook is formed in young people. On the other hand, the historical outlook enables young people to think analytically on a large scale.

References:

1. Маврулов А. Маънавий баркамол инсон тарбияси. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2008. –Б. 34.

- 2.Йўлдошев С., Усмонов М., Каримов Р. Янги ва энг янги давр Ғарбий Европа фалсафаси. – Т.: Шарқ, 2002. –Б. 83-84.
- 3.Фалсафа: қомусий луғат (Тузувчи ва масъул муҳаррир Қ.Назаров). – Т.: Шарқ, 2004. – Б. 390.
- 4.Ғозиев Э.Ғ. Тафаккур психологияси. – Т.:Ўқитувчи, 1990. – Б.3.
- 5.Усмонова Э.З. Ўқувчиларда мустақил тафаккурни қандай шакллантириш мумкин? – Т.: ТДПУ, 2000. – Б.3.
- 6.Шоназаров Қ.Р. Бўлажак тарих ўқитувчиларини мактаб ўқувчиларида тарихий тафаккурни шакллантиришга тайёрлаш: Пед. фан. ном. ... дис. – Т., 2002. –Б. 134.
- 7.Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. – Т.: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси нашриёти, 2008. – 608 б.
- 8.Ivanov P.I., Zufarova M.E. Umuiniy psixologiya. – Т.: O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, 2008. – 480 b.
- 9.Asatulloev, I. (2019). Erich Fromm's Theory On Alienation. Science and Education, 2, 1-9. 10.
- 11.Inomjon, A. (2019). The Issues of Alienation in the Philosophy of Erich Fromm. Canadian Social Science, 15(6), 31-34.
- 12.Asatulloev, I. (2019). The problem of alienation in the philosophy erich fromm. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(1), 123-129.
- 13.Asatulloev, I. A. (2022). A Comparative Analysis Of The Soul Concept Of Abu Hamid Ghazzali And Erich Fromm. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(10), 1996-2004.

